

Reproducing “User Preference-aware Fake News Detection”

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This paper constitutes a reproducibility study of the paper “User Preference-aware Fake News Detection” [2] by Dou et al. which proposes a framework to detect fake news. While this study could not reproduce results indicating a statistically significant superiority of the proposed framework over existing models, it observes a statistically significant advantage of modeling user endogenous preference. The code and workflow of this study can be found in the accompanied Jupyter Notebook.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The paper [2] proposes a framework, UPFD, which simultaneously captures various signals from user preferences by joint content and graph modeling. To that end, it employs two modules, END and EXO, for the respective encoding of endogenous and exogenous information. To reproduce the experimental setup, experiments, and results as explained in the paper, we employ the following strategy for each experiment.

- (1) **Analysis:** We first aim to holistically comprehend the experimental setup based on the information provided in the paper and on the official GitHub¹.
- (2) **Design:** Based on (1), we structure the experiments by reusing original implementations and elaborating reasonable substitutes where needed.
- (3) **Reproduction:** Based on (2), we execute the experiments and conclude the results.

In total, the paper conducts three experiments and we will discuss each experiment in a separate section, sections 3-5, applying the strategy introduced above. In section 2, we discuss commonalities across these experiments and conclude with a discussion in section 6.

2 COMMONALITIES

Experiments 1-3 share several structural properties which we will discuss in this section.

Dataset. Each experiment is conducted for two datasets contained in the FakeNewsNet dataset [11], *Politifact* and *Gossipcop*. Thus, the variable dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{\text{politifact}, \text{gossipcop}\}$ constitutes an independent variable. We note that the authors employ preprocessed versions, originally obtained from the *dg1* library (Deep Graph Library) [12], of these datasets which they provide on GitHub. Regarding user preference, the authors crawled Tweets that referenced elements of these datasets; this information source can only be accessed through dictionaries for privacy reasons.

Dependent variables. Each experiment has as dependent variables the accuracy and the F1-score on the test sets $D_{\text{test}; \mathcal{D}}$. Hence, the dependent variables are the performance metrics operationalizing the effect investigated and we

¹<https://github.com/safe-graph/GNN-FakeNews>

infer that the paper reports the *macro-averaged* F1-score. We will always report results associated with the dependent variables in percentages.

Evaluation. The paper states that each experimental result is averaged over five different runs. Based on that, we deduce that bootstrapping is performed and each run induces paired values for the dependent variables for each combination of independent variables based on a shared train-dev-test split. That is, given a dataset \mathcal{D} and a random seed s , one performs a shuffling of \mathcal{D} . The shuffled dataset is subsequently split² into (20%) a training set $D_{\text{train};\mathcal{D}}$, (10%) a development set $D_{\text{dev};\mathcal{D}}$ and (70%) a test set $D_{\text{test};\mathcal{D}}$. The paper does not provide information concerning the choice of random seeds; for our setup, each of the five runs has a one-to-one correspondence to the random seeds $s = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 777\}$.

Hypothesis testing. We note that the paper merely reports the mean performance metrics over the 5 runs, i.e., neither variance nor confidence intervals are reported. Contrary to the paper, we will report the mean over the five runs as well as the corresponding 95% confidence interval. Here, we account for the small sample size of $N = 5$ by employing the corresponding t -score. That is, with a probability of 95%, the true mean metric μ of the observed metric \bar{x} will be in the interval $[\bar{x} \pm t_4 \cdot \sigma_{\bar{x}}]$, where $t_4 = 2.776$ is the two-tailed t -value with degrees of freedom $df = 5 - 1$ and significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, and $\sigma_{\bar{x}}$ is the standard error estimated from the sample standard deviation. When the paper states to employ a t -test, we interpret this to be a *paired sample* t -test as it has the highest power for the setup described.

Implementation. All models are implemented using PyTorch, and all GNN models are implemented with the PyTorch-Geometric package [3]. Most of the methods employed in the paper’s experimental setup are provided on the official GitHub.

Platform. The paper does not specify the platform used for the experiments conducted. For our reproducibility study, we will use for each experiment the same runtime environment, i.e., a virtual machine hosted by CodeOcean³. We make use of the environment’s multi-GPU option for GNN models through the `DataLoader` of the PyTorch-Geometric package.

Hyperparameters. The paper reports using a unified graph embedding size (128), batch size (128), optimizer (Adam), and L2 regularization weight (0.001). Furthermore, hyper-parameters depending on (the factors) model and dataset are reported⁴ on the official GitHub. Staying as close as possible to the information provided, we will strictly use the information from both sources for our reproducibility study.

3 EXPERIMENT 1

- (1) **Analysis:** Experiment 1 is a factorial experiment to find the best combination of the modules END and EXO for UPFD across two datasets. The independent variables are (i) the module END={None (=profile information is used), word2vec [8], BERT [1]}, (ii) the module EXO={GraphSAGE [5], GCNFN [9]}, (iii) the dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{\text{politifact, gossipcop}\}$.
- (2) **Design:** The implementation and hyper-parameter information for all modules as well as the data(-preprocessing pipeline) has been available on GitHub. Since UPFD performs news concatenation by design, we set the boolean hyper-parameter `-concat` to true for all combinations. In Table 1, we list the settings used for structuring the experiment.

²We would like to draw attention to the unusual allocation of 20%-10%-70% for the train-dev-test split. In particular, the implementation provided on the official GitHub uses the development set merely to print intermediate performance metrics during the training phase. Although this is counter-intuitive in the light of maximizing test performance, we will employ this same setting for our reproducibility study.

³<https://codeocean.com/capsule/7305473/tree>

⁴https://github.com/safe-graph/GNN-FakeNews/blob/main/hyper_parameters.md

Model	Feature	Epoch	lr	Dataset	Concatenation
gnn.py -model 'sage'	profile	70	0.01	politifact	True
gnn.py -model 'sage'	spacy [7]	45	0.01	politifact	True
gnn.py -model 'sage'	bert	30	0.01	politifact	True
gcnfn.py	profile	80	0.001	politifact	True
gcnfn.py	spacy	50	0.001	politifact	True
gcnfn.py	bert	60	0.001	politifact	True
gnn.py -model 'sage'	profile	50	0.01	gossipcop	True
gnn.py -model 'sage'	spacy	80	0.001	gossipcop	True
gnn.py -model 'sage'	bert	80	0.001	gossipcop	True
gcnfn.py	profile	50	0.001	gossipcop	True
gcnfn.py	spacy	50	0.001	gossipcop	True
gcnfn.py	bert	50	0.001	gossipcop	True

Table 1. Experimental structure for Experiment 1.

- (3) **Reproduction:** We run the experiments as structured in Table 1 for the chosen seeds and report the results in Table 2. The paper concludes that Experiment 1 shows that the endogenous features (word2vec and BERT) are consistently better than the profile feature, which only encodes the user profile information. However, augmented with 95% confidence intervals, our results portray a more nuanced picture. Indeed, as seen in Table 2, large overlaps among the confidence intervals call into question such definite conclusions. To quantify this further, we conducted a paired sample t-test for the accuracy metric for the models (profile, GraphSAGE) and (word2vec, GraphSAGE) which resulted in a p -value of 0.41, reasonably refuting any claim of statistical significance. The paper proceeds to conclude that the model (GraphSAGE, BERT) has the average best performance among other models and feature variants. As can be seen in Table 2, this conclusion can only be drawn for the Gossipcop dataset, suggesting that the dataset attribute is not primable according to the PRIMAD model [4] and thus an overall lack of generalizability.

Feature	POL				GOS			
	GraphSAGE		GCNFN		GraphSAGE		GCNFN	
	ACC	F1	ACC	F1	ACC	F1	ACC	F1
profile	77.74 ± 1.664	77.56 ± 1.69	75.84 ± 3.42	75.64 ± 3.21	91.64 ± 1.99	91.57 ± 2.03	88.76 ± 1.31	88.68 ± 1.30
word2vec	78.91 ± 8.17	78.67% ± 8.37	83.08 ± 8.98	82.83 ± 9.32	<u>95.94</u> ± 1.33	<u>95.90</u> ± 1.35	93.59 ± 2.01	93.54 ± 2.00
BERT	<u>81.81</u> ± 7.09	<u>81.73</u> ± 6.99	79.00 ± 6.39	78.86 ± 6.48	96.66 ± 1.06	96.63 ± 1.08	95.50 ± 1.88	95.47 ± 1.92

Table 2. Results for Experiment 1.

4 EXPERIMENT 2

- (1) **Analysis:** Based on their conclusions from Experiment 1, the authors define the model (GraphSAGE, BERT) as "UPFD", which is used to perform a baseline comparison with models from the literature. The *implicit* hypothesis is that the average performance metrics associated with UPFD are significantly better than the next best model from the literature in Experiment 2. This is translated into the null hypotheses for the performance metrics of $H_0 : \mu_\delta = 0$, where μ_δ is the mean of differences of paired values; a paired sample t-test is performed to test it. The independent variables are (i) the model $m = \{m_1, m_2\}$ with $m_1 = \{\text{SAFE, CSI, BERT+MLP, word2vec+MLP}\}$, $m_2 =$

{GNN-CL [6], GCNFN, UPFD} and (ii) the dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{\text{politifact}, \text{gossipcop}\}$. The instances of m_1 constitute models that only encode news information ("News Only") whereas the instances of m_2 are models encoding both news and user information ("News+User"), e.g., the proposed model, UPFD.

(2) **Design:** The implementation and hyper-parameter information for the models of m_2 , i.e., GNN-CL and GCNFN, as well as the corresponding data(-preprocessing pipeline) has been available on GitHub. However, neither of these sources has been available for the models of m_1 . In particular, the following observations made us conclude that the "News Only" baselines are irreproducible:

- *SAFE*: This baseline model by Zhou et al. [13] incorporates image and textual information for fake news classification. To have a fair baseline comparison, the model was altered only to take the textual information into account. Although their code was released on GitHub⁵, from neither the implementation nor the paper it is clear how this existing model has been modified accordingly or how the dataset formats have been aligned with its architecture.
- *CSI*: This baseline model by Ruchansky et al. [10] employs an elaborate LSTM to encode the news content information to detect fake news and the original implementation is provided on GitHub⁶. However, the proposed architecture requires the data to be in a specific format to account for the time component of the news source. The paper we seek to reproduce does not specify how or whether the datasets employed have been processed to align with this architecture.
- *BERT+MLP*, *word2vec+MLP*: These two baseline models are vaguely defined, as neither the official GitHub nor the paper provides details regarding the parameters of the multilayer perceptron (MLP) such as the number of input/hidden/output layers or the criterion used. In addition, the paper does not specify how the graph data formats were adapted to account for an MLP architecture, which is very different in its data requirements from a GNN.

In Table 3, we list the settings used for structuring the experiment.

Model	Feature	Epoch	lr	Dataset	Concatenation
gnnc1.py	profile	60	0.001	politifact	-
gcnfn.py	content	100	0.001	politifact	False
gnnc1.py	profile	40	0.001	gossipcop	-
gcnfn.py	content	50	0.001	gossipcop	False

Table 3. Experimental structure for Experiment 2.

(3) **Reproduction:** We run the experiments as structured in Table 3 for the chosen seeds and report the results in Table 4. According to the average performance, UPFD constitutes the best model whereas GCNFN and GNN-CL share the second place depending on the dataset. However, the confidence intervals again exhibit large overlaps. We perform the corresponding paired sample t-tests regarding the accuracy metric per dataset, resulting in the p -values POL/ACC: 0.36 (UPFD vs. GCNFN) and GOS/ACC: 0.034 for (UPFD vs. GNN-CL). That is, we observe that UPFD is not, in a statistically significant manner, superior over the baselines with respect to the average performance across both datasets. In particular, the conclusion of statistical superiority can only be drawn with

⁵<https://github.com/Jindi0/SAFE>

⁶<https://github.com/sungyongs/CSI-Code>

respect to the Gossipcop dataset, again suggesting that the dataset attribute is not primable according to the PRIMAD model.

	Model	POL		GOS	
		ACC	F1	ACC	F1
News Only	SAFE	-	-	-	-
	CSI	-	-	-	-
	BERT+MLP	-	-	-	-
	word2vec+MLP	-	-	-	-
News + User	GNN-CL	63.98 ± 15.14	62.58 ± 16.59	95.04 ± 2.21	95.01 ± 2.23
	GCNFN	75.39 ± 32.89	71.48 ± 45.61	94.6 ± 5.16	94.56 ± 5.22
	UPFD (ours)	81.81 ± 7.09	81.73 ± 6.99	96.66 ± 1.06	96.63 ± 1.08

Table 4. Results for Experiment 2.

5 EXPERIMENT 3

- (1) **Analysis:** The paper performs an ablation study, fixing the model (GCNFN, word2vec) for both datasets, and removing news concatenation to ensure a fair comparison. The translated null hypothesis for the performance metrics is $H_0 : \mu_\delta = 0$, where μ_δ is the mean of differences of paired values which is tested via a paired sample t-test. The independent variables are (i) the model $m = \{(END, EXO), (-END, EXO), (END, -EXO), (-END, -EXO)\}$ and (ii) the dataset $\mathcal{D} = \{\text{politifact}, \text{gossipcop}\}$, where the prefix "-" describes the removal of the associated module.
- (2) **Design:** The implementation and hyper-parameter information as well as the corresponding data(-preprocessing pipeline) have been available on GitHub. To achieve -EXO, we remove all edges in the news propagation graph via⁷ the transform-operation `DropEdge(1, 1)` in the data-preprocessing pipeline. We achieve -END by employing the profile feature, which only encodes the user profile information. In Table 5, we list the settings used for structuring the experiment.

Model	Feature	Epoch	lr	Dataset	Concatenation	Transform
gcnfn.py	spacy	50	0.001	politifact	False	ToUndirected()
gcnfn.py	profile	50	0.001	politifact	False	ToUndirected()
gcnfn.py	spacy	50	0.001	politifact	False	DropEdge(1, 1)
gcnfn.py	profile	50	0.001	politifact	False	DropEdge(1, 1)
gcnfn.py	spacy	50	0.001	gossipcop	False	ToUndirected()
gcnfn.py	profile	50	0.001	gossipcop	False	ToUndirected()
gcnfn.py	spacy	50	0.001	gossipcop	False	DropEdge(1, 1)
gcnfn.py	profile	50	0.001	gossipcop	False	DropEdge(1, 1)

Table 5. Experimental structure for Experiment 3.

- (3) **Reproduction:** We run the experiments as structured in Table 5 for the chosen seeds and report the results in Table 6. The paper states that removing either component from the UPFD will reduce its performance. This conclusion has been drawn concerning the average performance metrics. Again, our results in Table 6 convey a

⁷We note that we inferred this step from the available code. Neither the paper nor the official GitHub provides information as to how to achieve the models used in the ablation study programmatically.

more nuanced picture. Indeed, we observe large overlaps of confidence intervals. We tested the null hypothesis $H_0 : \mu_\delta = 0$, where μ_δ is the mean of differences of paired values, with a paired sample t-test and reported the corresponding p -values in Table 7. We observe that the p -value of (END,EXO) vs. (END,-EXO) is merely smaller or equal to 0.9 for both datasets. This calls into question, from a statistical point of view, the paper’s definite claim that jointly encoding the endogenous and exogenous information attains the best performance. In this context, Table 7 challenges the authors’ claim that all results are statistically significant under the t-test with $p \leq 0.01$. Similar to the paper, we observe a larger performance drop concerning the average metrics on Politifact when removing exogenous information. However, we do not conclude that this is an indication that this source is more informative on Politifact due to the high p -value of 0.839. Finally, based on Tables 6 & 7, we are able to support the paper’s conclusion that endogenous information contributes more to performance gain than exogenous information.

Model	POL		GOS	
	ACC	F1	ACC	F1
(END,EXO)	82.35 ± 7.87	82.09 ± 8.28	93.75 ± 1.34	93.71 ± 1.34
(-END,EXO)	76.92 ± 3.55	76.75 ± 3.52	88.79 ± 1.33	88.71 ± 1.31
(END,-EXO)	81.81 ± 7.47	81.51 ± 8.31	93.46 ± 6.36	93.39 ± 6.47
(-END,-EXO)	76.2 ± 2.59	76.03 ± 2.64	87.19 ± 1.03	87.09 ± 1.05

Table 6. Results for experiment 3.

	Model	(END,EXO)	(-END,EXO)	(END,-EXO)	(-END,-EXO)
POL	(END,EXO)	-	0.008	0.839	0.0197
	(-END,EXO)	-	-	0.0449	0.382
	(END,-EXO)	-	-	-	0.0138
GOS	(END,EXO)	-	5.14e-5	0.835	5.533
	(-END,EXO)	-	-	0.018	0.0022
	(END,-EXO)	-	-	-	0.0035

Table 7. p -values for accuracy of Table 6.

6 DISCUSSION

We conclude that the information disseminated in the paper and on the official GitHub is mostly sufficient to reproduce the paper’s experiment section. However, we note that the details provided with respect to the baseline comparison of models encoding only news information are insufficient to reproduce the results. We deduce that the values reported in the paper are likely to stem from the distribution sampled by our reproduced experiments. However, statistically significant differences mostly cannot be made out between the different settings. A potential reason for this could be a difference in the statistical testing procedure as the authors do not specify the exact t-test applied. Furthermore, the paper relies on averaged performance metrics to draw its conclusions, not taking into account variance or confidence intervals. Thereby, statistically significant results indicating the superiority of the proposed framework over existing models could not be reproduced. This reproducibility study, however, supports the main conclusion of the paper, confirming a statistically significant advantage of modeling the user endogenous preference.

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